

**A CHEBYSHEV COLLOCATION TECHNIQUE FOR THE
NUMERICAL SOLUTION OF VOLTERRA INTEGRAL
EQUATIONS WITH APPLICATION TO VISCOELASTIC
PROBLEM**

BY

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**A PROJECT SUBMITTED TO THE DEPARTMENT OF
MATHEMATICS, UNIVERSITY OF LAGOS, AKOKA. IN PARTIAL
FULFILLMENT OF THE REQUIREMENTS OF THE AWARD OF
THE DEGREE OF BACHELOR OF SCIENCE (BSc.) IN
MATHEMATICS**

MAY, 2023

DEDICATION

I dedicate this project work to Almighty God, to my parents, Mr & Mrs Alimi, to my supervisor, Prof. Odekunle, Dr. Ehigie, to Larry Page, to Ijad Madisch and to myself.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

With profound gratitude, I thank God for all he's been doing in my life and for making this project a success.

I want to thank me for not giving up even though it hasn't been easy balancing work and school and sometimes i just feel like doing nothing but i kept pushing till the end.

Special thanks to my parents, i won't be here without them, for their sacrifices and encouragements, for being there for me and supporting me always.

I am grateful to my supervisor, Prof. Odekunle, for his support, attention, patience and thorough supervision of this project, for making me develop interest in computational maths and making it easy for me, for believing in me and not just being a lecturer but a father and to Dr. Ehigie for adopting me when my supervisor was not around and for guiding me and making my work easier.

Finally, I'll like to appreciate all the lecturers that I've been oppertuned to learn from throughout my stay in this school, i say a big thank you and may God continue to be with you and your loved ones.

Amen.

ABSTRACT

Accurate modeling of viscoelasticity remains an important consideration for a variety of materials. As such, over the previous decades a substantial body of work has been dedicated to developing appropriate constitutive models for viscoelasticity. The Volterra integral equations arising from viscoelasticity have proven to be very difficult to solve directly, hence, the need for an accurate numerical method of solving them. This project presents a technique that converts a Volterra integral equation into a system of equations using shifted Chebyshev polynomials on $[0, 1]$ as basis function, it is tested on the Volterra integral equation arising from a viscoelastic model and produced an accurate result. Examples are given to explain the method of solution.

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1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of Study

An integral equation is a mathematical expression that includes a required function under an integration sign. Such equations often describe an elementary or a complex physical process wherein the characteristics at a given point depend on values in the whole domain and can not be defined only on the bases of the values near the given point (as in local-type problems described by differential equations) (Corduneanu, 1991). Linear integral equations are of the form:

$$A(x)y(x) + \int k(x, s)y(s)ds = f(x) \quad (1)$$

Where function A is called a coefficient; k is a kernel; and f is a free term of the equation. If $f(x) = 0$, Eq. (1) is called homogeneous; otherwise it is a non-homogeneous equation. Two kinds of linear integral equations may be distinguished depending on whether $A(x) = 0$ (first kind), $A(x) \neq 0$ for all x (second kind). The linear integral equation is said to be Volterra if at least one or both limit of integration is a variable, a linear Volterra integral equation of the second kind is of the form:

$$y(x) + \int_k^x k(x, s)y(s)ds = f(x) \quad (2)$$

Fourier, J. (1768-1830) is the initiator of the theory of integral equations. A term integral equation first suggested by Du Bois-Reymond in 1888. Du Bois-Reymond defined an integral equation is understood as an equation in which the unknown function occurs under one or more signs of definite integration. Late eighteenth and early ninetieth century Laplace, Fourier, Poission, Liouville and Able studied some special

type of integral equation. The pioneering systematic investigations goes back to late nineteenth and early twentieth century work of Volterra, Fredholm and Hilbert. In 1887, Volterra published a series of famous papers in which he singled out the notion of a functional and pioneered in the development of a theory of functional is in theory of linear integral equation of special type. Fredholm presented the fundamentals of the Fredholm integral equation theory in a paper published in 1903 in the *Acta Mathematica*. Hilbert followed Fredholm's paper with a series of papers in the *Nachrichten of the Göttingen Academy* (Mical, 1998).

The early history of Volterra equations dates back to the late 19th and early 20th centuries when Vito Volterra, an Italian mathematician, made significant contributions to the field of integral equations. Volterra's work laid the foundation for the study of integral equations and their applications in various scientific disciplines. Volterra's interest in integral equations emerged during his early academic career, in 1887, he published a paper titled "Sui sistemi di equazioni integrali e sulle loro applicazioni" (On systems of integral equations and their applications), which introduced the concept of integral equations and their significance in solving real-world problems. In this seminal work, Volterra investigated the behavior of systems of integral equations and proposed new techniques for their solution. He demonstrated that integral equations could describe a wide range of phenomena, including electromagnetic fields, heat conduction, population dynamics, and chemical reactions. One of the most important contributions by Volterra was the introduction of what is now known as Volterra integral equations. These equations involve an unknown function within an integral and describe the dependence of a variable on its past values, allowing for the modeling of cumulative effects. Volterra's research on integral equations gained recognition and acclaim within the scientific community. He was appointed as a pro-

fessor of mathematical physics at the University of Rome in 1892 and continued to make significant advancements in the field. The Volterra integral equations were then studied by Traian Lalescu in his 1908 thesis, *Sur les équations de Volterra*, written under the direction of Émile Picard. In 1911, Lalescu wrote the first book ever on integral equations. During the early 20th century, Volterra's investigations into integral equations expanded further, leading to the development of the theory of functional equations. He explored the properties of nonlinear integral equations and introduced the concept of kernels, which describe the relationship between the unknown function and the integral. Volterra integral equations find application in demography, the study of viscoelastic materials, and in actuarial science through the renewal equation (Arfken, 1985).

Of particular interest are Volterra integral of the Hammerstein type, several authors have applied various techniques for approximating the solution of these types of equations (Crisci, Kolmanovskii, Russo & Vecchio, 2000). Viscoelasticity is the property of materials that exhibit both viscous and elastic characteristics when undergoing deformation. Viscous materials, like honey, resist shear flow and strain linearly with time when a stress is applied. Elastic materials strain instantaneously when stretched and just as quickly return to their original state once the stress is removed. Viscoelastic materials have elements of both of these properties and, as such, exhibit time dependent strain. Whereas elasticity is usually the result of bond stretching along crystallographic planes in an ordered solid, viscoelasticity is the result of the diffusion of atoms or molecules inside of an amorphous material (Meyers & Chawla, 1999).

In the nineteenth century, physicists such as Maxwell, Boltzmann, and Kelvin researched and experimented with creep and recovery of glasses, metals, and rubbers.

Viscoelasticity was further examined in the late twentieth century when synthetic polymers were engineered and used in a variety of applications. Viscoelasticity calculations depend heavily on the viscosity variable, η . The inverse of η is also known as fluidity, ψ . The value of either can be derived as a function of temperature or as a given value (Christensen, 1948). There are two types of Viscoelasticity: linear and non-linear viscoelasticity. Linear viscoelasticity is when the function is separable in both creep response and load and is usually applicable to small deformations. All linear viscoelastic models can be represented by a Volterra equation connecting stress and strain:

$$\sigma(t) = E_{inst,relax}\epsilon(t) + \int_0^t F(t-t')\epsilon(t')dt' \quad (3)$$

where, t is time, $\sigma(t)$ is stress, $\epsilon(t)$ is strain, $E_{inst,relax}$ is the instantaneous elastic moduli for relaxation, $F(t)$ is the relaxation function. Nonlinear viscoelasticity is when the function is not separable. It usually happens when the deformations are large or if the material changes its properties under deformations (Roylance, 2001).

The study and analysis of mathematical models of linear viscoelastic materials is to investigate the relationship between input (stress or strain) on such materials and output (strain or stress) that occurs from the response of such materials. Generally, the mathematical models used for linear viscoelastic materials are the Maxwell model, the Kevin-Voigt model and the standard linear model in which all these models cannot accurately describe the properties of linear viscoelastic materials (Jiraphon, 2007). If the current response depends on the earlier history of the stress– strain dynamics of the material (i.e. the material has memory), then Volterra integral equations become the natural framework within which to model the response. For viscoelastic

materials, when the response is linear, the dual linear Boltzmann causal integral equations are the appropriate model. The choice of one rather than the other depends on whether the applied deformation is a stress or a strain, and the associated response is, respectively, a creep or a relaxation. The duality between creep and relaxation is known explicitly and is referred to as the ‘interconversion equation’.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

The importance of a fast and accurate method of solution of Volterra-Hammerstein equation that arises from modeling of viscoelasticity can not be oversized. Researchers continue to improve on the method of solution; of which this work is an attempt.

This work introduces a modification of the Chebyshev collocation method of solving integral equations, the shifted Chebyshev collocation method, and applies it to solve problems on Volterra equations.

1.3 Aim and Objectives

The aim of this work is to provide solution to viscoelastic problem using Chebyshev collocation method. The specific objectives are:

1. to illustrate with some examples using shifted Chebyshev polynomials as basis function in solving Volterra integral equations.
2. to apply the method to solving a viscoelastic model.
3. to interpret the result.

1.4 Scope of the Study

The practical application of orthogonal polynomials is used to find an approximate solution to Volterra integral equations of all kinds with algebraic kernel and

applied to solving a viscoelastic model showing that numerical analysis is meant to solve real life problems and problems arising from real life models.

1.5 Significance of the Study

Many problems arising in mathematics and in particular, applied mathematics can be formulated into two distinct but connected ways: Differential equations and Integral equations. Over the years, much emphasis has been placed on the solution of Differential Equations (Ordinary Differential Equations and Partial Differential Equations) more than the solution of integral equations because the solution of integral equations has proven to be more tasking to obtain compared to the differential equations.

According to (Ramm, 2009) , Integral equations can be used as the mathematical model in which many physical problems are modelled. The numerical solution of such integral equations has been studied by various authors and in recent years, great works have been focused on the development of more advanced and efficient methods for integral equations as they have several applications.

This project studies the shifted Chebyshev collocation method of solving Volterra equations and applies a modification of the study to solve the Volterra-Hammerstein integral equation that arises from the model of viscoelasticity and the result is compared to the exact solution of the model.

1.6 Definition of Some Terms

1. Differential Equations: This is an equation with one or more derivatives of a function.
2. Partial Differential Equations: This is an equation that involves two or more independent variables, an unknown dependent variable and partial derivative of the unknown function with respect to the independent variables.
3. Integral Equations: These are equations in which the unknown function to be found lies within an integral sign.
4. Linear Integral Equations: Linear integral equations are integral equations of the form;

$$A(x)y(x) + \int k(x, s)y(s)ds = f(x).$$

5. Linear Volterra Equations: A linear integral equation is said to be Volterra if at least one or both limit of integration is a variable.
6. Integro-differential Equation: This is a mathematical expression which contains derivatives of the required function and its integral transforms.
7. Volterra-Hammerstein Integral Equations: These are integral equations of the form;

$$y(t) + \int k(t, s)H(s, x(s))ds = x(t).$$

8. Stress: This is defined as force per unit area within materials that arise from externally applied forces, uneven heating, or permanent deformation and that permits an accurate description and prediction of elastic, plastic, and fluid behavior.

9. Strain: This is the amount of deformation experienced by the body in the direction of force applied, divided by the initial dimensions of the body.
10. Mathematical Models: This is an abstract model that uses mathematical language to describe the behavior of a system.
11. Orthogonal Polynomials: These are classes of polynomials $p_n(x)$ defined over a range (a,b) that obey an orthogonality relation;

$$\int_a^b w(x)p_n(x)p_m(x)dx = \delta_{mn}c_n,$$

Where $w(x)$ is the weight function and δ_{mn} is the Kronecker-delta, if $c_n = 1$, then it is not just orthogonal but also orthonormal.

12. Power Series: This is a function which has the form of a polynomial with infinitely many terms.
13. Taylor Series: This is a power series that gives the expansion of a function $f(x)$ in the neighborhood of a point a provided that in the neighborhood the function is continuous, all its derivatives exist.
14. Collocation Method: This is a method for the numerical solution of ordinary differential equations, partial differential equations and integral equations.
15. Dirichlet Problems: This is the problem of finding a function which solves a specified Partial Differential Equation (PDE) in the interior of a given region that takes prescribed values on the boundary of the region.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Integral Equations

Integral equations arise naturally in physics, chemistry, biology and engineering applications such as diffraction problems, scattering in quantum mechanics, conformal mapping, water waves, viscoelasticity, etc. Integral equations arise as representation forms of differential equations. A large class of initial and boundary value problems can be converted to integral equations. Integral equations of various types play an important role in many branches of functional analysis and in their applications. The potential theory contributed more than any field to integral equations. A typical form of an integral equation in $u(x)$ is of the form:

$$u(x) = f(x) + \int_{\beta(x)}^{\alpha(x)} k(x, t)u(t)dt \quad (4)$$

where $K(x, t)$ is called the kernel of the integral equation, and $\alpha(x)$ and $\beta(x)$ are the limits of integration. It is easily observed that the unknown function $u(x)$ appears under the integral sign as stated in equation 4, and out of the integral sign in most other cases. It is also important to point out that the kernel $k(x, t)$ and the function $f(x)$ in equation 1 are given in advance. Linear integral equations are of the form:

$$A(x)y(x) + \int k(x, t)y(t)dt = f(x). \quad (5)$$

Where function A is called a coefficient; k is a kernel; and f is a free term of the equation. If $f(x) = 0$, Eq. (3) is called homogeneous; otherwise it is a non-homogeneous equation. Two kinds of linear integral equations may be distinguished depending on whether $A(x) = 0$ (first kind), $A(x) \neq 0$ for all x (second kind). The most fre-

quently used linear integral equations fall under two main classes namely Fredholm and Volterra integral equations, however there are different types;

1. Fredholm integral equations
2. Volterra integral equations
3. Integro-differential equations
4. Singular integral equations
5. Volterra-Fredholm integral equations
6. Volterra-Fredholm integro-differential equations

The systems of integral equations are usually difficult to solve directly so a numerical method is often needed. In such cases, it is required to get the approximate solutions; and many different numerical techniques have been developed and presented during decades of research, with appropriate combinations of numerical integration and interpolation procedures. In order to approximate numerically the solution of general integral equations, the predominant technique have been the use of some kind of Piecewise Constant Basis Functions (PCBFs) and Chebyshev polynomial (Elnagar, Kazemi & Chebyshev, 1996). However, after a long period of time many other techniques have attracted much attention recently; like wavelets theory that started with the introduction of Haar function in 1910. From 1990s, (Crandal, 1992) many wavelet type methods have been applied for solving integral equations. Haar wavelets, despite its relative simplicity, have many valued properties: as its compact support and orthogonality properties. More recently, several numerical methods based on different triangular type and delta orthogonal functions were designed for approximating the solution of integral Volterra equations (Roodaki, 2012). All these publications have demonstrated and revealed that these techniques based on PCBF and wavelets are effective to obtain the solution of such integral equations. Particularly, systems of

linear integral equations and their exact or approximate solutions, are of great importance in science and engineering.

There are several numerical methods for solving systems of linear Volterra integral equations of the second kind, and they have been often solved by classical numerical and analytical methods: such as Galerkin and finite element methods, collocation and spectral methods, Taylor or Power series and expansion methods, transforming the equations into a linear or nonlinear system of algebraic equations, and so on. However, new methods also have been applied to solve them, like the homotopy perturbation method (Ghasemi, 2007), Adomian decomposition method and many others (Wazwaz, 2010), use of Legendre wavelets (Yousefi, 2005) or hybrid Legendre and block pulse functions (Maleknejad, 2002), Chebyshev polynomials (El-Borai, 2008), Radial basis function (Pedro, Miguel Basim, 2022), etc. Furthermore, there are also expansion methods for integral equations such as El-gendi's and Wolfe's methods. Additionally, the approximate solutions of systems of integral equations that usually appear in problems of physics, biology and engineering are based on numerical integration methods: such as Euler–Chebyshev or Runge–Kutta methods (Yusbasi, 2011).

2.1.1 Fredholm Integral Equations

The standard form of Fredholm linear integral equations, where the limits of integration a and b are constants, are given by the form;

$$A(x)u(x) = f(x) + \lambda \int_a^b k(x, t)u(t)dt. \quad a \leq x, t \leq b. \quad (6)$$

where the kernel of the integral equation $k(x, t)$ and the function $f(x)$ are given in advance. The equation is called linear because the unknown function $u(x)$ under the integral sign occurs linearly, i.e. the power of $u(x)$ is one. The value of $A(x)$ will give

the following kinds of Fredholm linear integral equations:

1. First kind: when $A(x) = 0$

$$f(x) + \lambda \int_a^b k(x, t)u(t)dt = 0 \quad (7)$$

2. Second kind: when $A(x) = 1$

$$u(x) = f(x) + \lambda \int_a^b k(x, t)u(t)dt \quad (8)$$

In fact, the second kind can be obtained from by dividing both sides of the general form by $A(x)$ provided that $A(x) \neq 0$. In summary, the Fredholm integral equation is of the first kind if the unknown function $u(x)$ appears only under the integral sign. However, the Fredholm integral equation is of the second kind if the unknown function $u(x)$ appears inside and outside the integral sign.

2.1.2 Volterra Integral Equations

The standard form of Volterra linear integral equations, where the limits of integration are functions of x rather than constants, are of the form;

$$A(x)u(x) = f(x) + \lambda \int_a^x k(x, t)u(t)dt. \quad a \leq x, t \leq b. \quad (9)$$

It is worth noting that Volterra integral equations can be viewed as a special case of Fredholm integral equation when the kernel $k(x, t)$ vanishes for $t > x$, x is in the range of integration (a, b) . Volterra integral equations fall under two kinds, depending on the value of $A(x)$, namely;

1. When $A(x)=0$,

$$f(x) + \lambda \int_a^x k(x,t)u(t)dt = 0. \quad (10)$$

and this is called Volterra integral equation of the first kind.

2. When $A(x) = 1$,

$$u(x) = f(x) + \lambda \int_a^x k(x,t)u(t)dt \quad (11)$$

and this is called Volterra integral equation of the second kind.

Volterra integral equations arise in many usual applications of technology, engineering and science in general: as in population dynamics, viscoelasticity, the spread of epidemics, some Dirichlet problems in potential theory, electrostatics, mathematical modeling of radioactive equilibrium, the particle transport problems of astrophysics and reactor theory, radiative energy and/or heat transfer problems, other general heat transfer problems, oscillation of strings and membranes, the problem of momentum representation in quantum mechanics, etc. However, many other complex problems of mathematics, chemistry, biology, astrophysics and mechanics, can be expressed in the terms of Volterra integral equations. Some practical problems, where impulses arise naturally (like in population dynamics or many biological applications) or are caused by some control system (like viscoelastic problems and simulations of semiconductor devices) can be modeled by a differential equation, an integral equation, an integro-differential equation, or a system of these equations all combined. Furthermore, Fredholm and Volterra integral equations arise from different origins and applications, such as boundary value problems as in Fredholm equations, and from initial value problems as in Volterra equations. Based on the fact that integral equations arise from distinct origins, different techniques and approaches will be used

to determine the solution of each type of integral equations.

2.1.3 Integro-differential Equations

Volterra, in the early 1900, studied the population growth, where new type of equations have been developed and was termed integro-differential equations. In this type of equations, the unknown function $u(x)$ occurs in one side as an ordinary derivative, and appears on the other side under the integral sign. Several phenomena in physics and biology (He, 2006) give rise to this type of integro-differential equations. It is pointed out that an integro-differential equation can be easily observed as an intermediate stage when converting a differential equation to an integral equation. The following are examples of integro-differential equations:

$$u''(x) = -x + \int_0^x (x-t)u(t)dt, \quad u(0) = 0, u'(0) = 1. \quad (12)$$

$$u'(x) = 1 - x + \int_0^1 (xt)u(t)dt, \quad u(0) = 1. \quad (13)$$

Equation 12 is a Volterra integro-differential equations, and equation 13 is a Fredholm integro-differential equation. This classification has been concluded as a result of the limits of integration.

2.1.4 Singular Integral Equations

A singular integral equation is an equation in which one or both limits of the integration are infinite at one or more points within the range of integration. For example, the integral equation:

$$u(x) = f(x) + \lambda \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} k(x, t)u(t)dt \quad (14)$$

1. Weakly singular integral equation: If the kernel of the form

$$k(x, t) = \frac{H(x, t)}{|x - t|^\alpha}$$

OR

$$k(x, t) = H(x, t) \ln |x - t|$$

where $H(x, t)$ is bounded, $a \leq x \leq b$ and $a \leq t \leq b$ with $H(x, t) \neq 0$ and α is a constant between 0 and 1 i.e. $0 < \alpha < 1$.

2. Strongly singular integral equation: If the kernel of the form

$$k(x, t) = \frac{H(x, t)}{|x - t|^2}$$

and $H(x, t)$ is a non-zero differentiable function of (x, t)

2.2 Collocation Method

Many problems arising in mathematics and in particular, applied mathematics can be formulated into two distinct but connected ways: differential equations and integral equations. Over the years, much emphasis has been placed on the solution of differential equations (ordinary differential equations and partial differential equations) more than the solution of integral equations because one may easily accept that the solution of integral equations are more tasking to obtain compared to the differential equations. According to (Brunner, 2004). Integral equations can be used as the mathematical model in which many physical problems are modelled. The numerical solution of such integral equations has been studied by various authors and in recent years, great works have been focused on the development of more advanced and efficient methods for integral equations as they have several applications.

Mathematicians have so far devoted their attention mainly to two peculiarly types of integral equations: the linear integral equations of the first and second kinds. Collocation method involves evaluation of approximate solution in a suitable set of functions called basis function or trial solution. This method for obtaining the approximate solution to an integral equation has its origin in the 1930s when Kantorovic in 1934 considered an integral equation using the line collocation procedure. Viladson and Stewart in 1967 used orthogonal collocation to solve a boundary value problems where the set of orthogonal polynomials was developed using both the boundary conditions and the roots of the polynomials as the collocation points. Recently, many researchers have developed the numerical method to obtain the solution to an integral equation using several well known polynomials and in particular, orthogonal polynomials. Rahman (2003) obtained the numerical solution of the Volterra integral equation of second kind using the Galerkin method and he used the Hermite polynomials as the basis function. Similarly, Islam and Rahman (2013) explored the solution of both the linear and nonlinear Volterra integral equation using the Galerkin method but they used the Hermite and Chebyshev polynomials as the basis function. Reifenberg and Berrut (2000) also considered the first kind boundary integral equation and obtained its numerical solution by the means of attenuation factors. Cellorio and Sayas (2001) did a work by using an extrapolation techniques and collocation method for some integral equations. Atkinson (1997) obtained a numerical solution of the integral equation of second kind and he compared the error with that of analytical solution. Yusuf and Elbas (2008) uses the numerical expansion methods to solve Fredholm-Volterra linear integral equation by interpolation and quadrature rules while Ramm (2009) formulated and used the collocation technique to obtain the numerical solution of the Fredholm second kind integral equation.

2.2.1 Basis Functions

A basis function is an element of a particular basis for a function space. In the conversion of integral equations to system of algebraic equations basis functions such as the orthogonal polynomials are needed. Orthogonal Polynomials are classes of polynomials $p_n(x)$ defined over a range (a,b) that obey an orthogonality relation;

$$\int_a^b w(x)p_m(x)p_n(x)dx = \delta_{mn}c_n \quad (15)$$

Where $w(x)$ is the weight function and δ_{mn} is the Kronecker-delta, if $c_n=1$ then it is not just orthogonal but also orthonormal. Some examples of orthogonal polynomials include;

1. Legendre polynomials (named after Adrien-Marie Legendre, who discovered them in 1782) are a system of complete and orthogonal polynomials, with a vast number of mathematical properties, and numerous applications. They can be defined as the coefficients in a formal expansion in powers of t of the generating function;

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{1-2xt+t^2}} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} P_n(x)t^n \quad (16)$$

The coefficient of t^n is a polynomial in x of degree n. Expanding gives $P_0(x) = 1$, $P_1(x) = x$.

Expansion to higher orders gets increasingly cumbersome, but is possible to do systematically, and again leads to one of the explicit forms given as;

$$(n+1) P_{n+1}(x) = (2n+1)xP_n(x) - nP_{n-1}(x) \quad \forall n \geq 1.$$

This relation, along with the first two polynomials P_0 and P_1 , allows all the rest to be generated recursively (El Attar & Refaat, 2009).

2. Laguerre Polynomials named after Edmond Laguerre (1834–1886) are solutions of Laguerre’s equation;

$$xy'' + (1 - x)y' + ny = 0.$$

which is a second-order linear differential equation. This equation has non-singular solutions only if n is a non-negative integer. Sometimes the name Laguerre polynomials is used for solutions of;

$$xy'' + (\alpha + 1 - x)y' + ny = 0.$$

The Laguerre polynomials can be defined recursively, given the first two polynomials as $L_0(x) = 1$, $L_1(x) = 1 - x$ by;

$$L_{k+1}(x) = \frac{(2k+1-x)L_k(x) - kL_{k-1}(x)}{k+1} \quad \forall k \geq 1.$$

This relation along with the initial values allows the rest to be generated (Szegő, 1975).

3. Chebyshev polynomials are two sequences of polynomials related to the cosine and sine functions, notated as $T_n(x)$ and $U_n(x)$. The Chebyshev polynomials of the first kind are given by $T_n(\cos x) = \cos(nx)$, similarly the second kind is given by $U_n(\cos x \sin x) = \sin((n+1)x)$. These definitions do not appear to be polynomials, but by using various trigonometric identities they can be converted to an explicitly polynomial form. For example, for $n = 2$ the T_2 formula can be converted into a polynomial with argument $x = \cos(x)$, using the double-angle formula:

$$\cos(2x) = 2\cos^2x - 1$$

replacing \cos with x gives

$$T_2(x) = 2x^2 - 1,$$

The other T_n can be defined similarly.

The Chebyshev polynomials T_n are polynomials with the largest possible leading coefficient, whose absolute value on the interval $[1, 1]$ is bounded by 1. Chebyshev

polynomials are important in approximation theory because the roots of $T_n(x)$, which are also called Chebyshev nodes, are used as matching points for optimizing polynomial interpolation. The resulting interpolation polynomial minimizes the problem of Runge's phenomenon and provides an approximation that is close to the best polynomial approximation to a continuous function under the maximum norm, also called the "min-max" criterion. The Chebyshev polynomials of the first kind can be generated by the recurrence formula;

$$T_0(x) = 1, T_1(x) = x, T_{n+1}(x) = 2xT_n(x) - T_{n-1}(x) \quad \forall n \geq 1.$$

The first six terms of the first kind of Chebyshev polynomials are;

$$T_0(x) = 1$$

$$T_1(x) = x$$

$$T_2(x) = 2x^2 - 1$$

$$T_3(x) = 4x^3 - 3x$$

$$T_4(x) = 8x^4 - 8x^2 + 1$$

$$T_5(x) = 16x^5 - 20x^3 + 5x$$

The ordinary generating functions for T_n is;

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} T_n(x) t^n = \frac{1-tx}{1+2tx+t^2}.$$

The Chebyshev polynomials of the second kind can be generated by the recurrence formula;

$$U_0(x) = 1, U_1(x) = 2x, U_{n+1}(x) = 2xU_n(x) - U_{n-1}(x) \quad \forall n \geq 1.$$

The first six terms of the second kind of Chebyshev polynomials are;

$$U_0(x) = 1$$

$$U_1(x) = 2x$$

$$U_2(x) = 4x^2 - 1$$

$$U_3(x) = 8x^3 - 4x$$

$$U_4(x) = 16x^4 - 12x^2 + 1$$

$$U_5(x) = 32x^5 - 32x^3 + 6x$$

The ordinary generating functions for U_n is;

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} U_n(x)t^n = \frac{1-tx}{1+2tx+t^2}.$$

Shifted Chebyshev polynomials are also of interest when the range of the independent variable is $[a, b]$ instead of $[-1, 1]$. The shifted Chebyshev polynomials of the first kind are defined as

$$T^*(x) = T_n\left(\frac{2}{b-a}x - \frac{b+a}{b-a}\right), \quad a \leq x \leq b, n \geq 0.$$

2.3 Viscoelastic Problems

Accurate modeling of viscoelasticity remains an important consideration for a variety of materials (e.g. polymers and inorganic glasses). As such, over the previous decades a substantial body of work has been dedicated to developing appropriate constitutive models for viscoelasticity ranging from initial considerations of linear thermo-viscoelasticity to more complex non-linear formulations incorporating fictive temperatures or potential energy clocks including the use of both Internal State Variable (ISV) and hereditary integral representations (Caruthers, Adolf, Chambers Shrikhande, 2004). Nonetheless, relatively limited (in comparison to plasticity) attention has been paid to the numerical integration of such schemes. In terms of integral based formulations, Taylor in 1982 first considered the problem of the integration of a linear viscoelasticity model. That work focused on the integration of the hereditary integrals and demonstrated improved performance of the new scheme with a custom finite element code over an existing finite difference reference. Chambers and Becker in 1986 using a free volume based shift factor also considered the integration of

the hereditary integrals and the impact on the problem of a pressurized thick-walled cylinder and developed an adaptive scheme to bound the error. R. Chambers in 1992 later developed three-point Gauss and composite integration schemes for the hereditary integrals and noted improved accuracy. With respect to ISV-based schemes, formulations for the non-linear Schapery model have been proposed (Muliana Khan, 2008). However, in those efforts greater attention was paid to convergence of the non-linear solution scheme than impact of numerical integration. Various authors have also studied the use of convolution integrals with differential forms of ISVs for temperature-independent formulations. A theory of linear viscoelasticity can be built by considering simple linear elements such as the (elastic) linear spring and the (viscous) linear dash pot. Several researchers have come up with different mathematical model for viscoelasticity, generally, the mathematical models used for linear viscoelastic materials are the Maxwell model, the Kelvin-Voigt model and the standard linear model in which all these models cannot accurately describe the properties of linear viscoelastic materials. For instance, the Maxwell model does not show the recovery behavior of materials, the Kelvin-Voigt model does not demonstrate the stress relaxation and the standard linear model can be applied well only for solid materials that has 100% recovery. Of particular interest is the linear non convolution Volterra equation arising from the model of a viscoelastic rod bending quasi statically derived by Reynolds, Appleby and Gyori in 2007.

3 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Shifted Chebyshev Polynomial on [0, 1]

Shifted Chebyshev polynomials are also of interest when the range of the independent variable is $[a, b]$ instead of $[1, 1]$. The shifted Chebyshev polynomials of the first kind are defined as

$$T_n^*(x) = T_n\left(\frac{2}{b-a}x - \frac{b+a}{b-a}\right), \quad a \leq x \leq b, \quad n \geq 0.$$

For $[0,1]$, $a = 0$ and $b = 1$, substituting this gives; $T_n^*(x) = T_n(2x - 1)$

where $T_n(x)$ are the Chebyshev orthogonal polynomials of the first kind and normalized by the requirement that $T_n^*(1) = 1$, T_n^* satisfies the three-term recurrence relation;

$$T_{n+1}^*(x) = 2(2x - 1)T_n^*(x) - T_{n-1}^*(x) \text{ for } n \geq 1,$$

with starting values $T_0^*(x) = 1$, $T_1^*(x) = 2x - 1$

Thus we have for the first few polynomials

$$T_0^*(x) = 1$$

$$T_1^*(x) = 2x - 1$$

$$T_2^*(x) = 2(2x - 1)(2x - 1) - 1 = 8x^2 - 8x + 1$$

$$T_3^*(x) = 2(2x - 1)(8x^2 - 8x + 1) - (2x - 1) = 32x^3 - 48x^2 + 18x - 1$$

$$T_4^*(x) = 2(2x - 1)(32x^3 - 48x^2 + 18x - 1) - (8x^2 - 8x + 1) = 128x^4 - 256x^3 + 160x^2 - 32x + 1$$

$$T_5^*(x) = 2(2x - 1)(128x^4 - 256x^3 + 160x^2 - 32x + 1) - (32x^3 - 48x^2 + 18x - 1) = 512x^5 - 1280x^4 + 1120x^3 - 400x^2 + 46x - 1.$$

3.2 Shifted Chebyshev Solution of Volterra Integral Equations

The source function $f(t)$ and the kernel function $a(t,s)$ are given, and $y(t)$, $y(s)$ are the unknown functions. In order that the solutions of the Volterra integral equation be sufficiently smooth, it is necessary to use very high-order numerical methods such as collocation methods for approximating the solution. In this method, Volterra integral equation is converted to a system of algebraic equations using Chebyshev polynomials as basis function i.e substituting the shifted Chebyshev on $[0,1]$ as $y(t)$.

Let $y(t) = \sum_{i=0}^n \alpha_i T_i^*(t)$, using case $n = 5$ gives;

$y(t) = \sum_{i=0}^5 \alpha_i T_i^*(t)$, where,

$$T_0^*(t) = 1, T_1^*(t) = 2t - 1, T_2^*(t) = 8t^2 - 8t + 1, T_3^*(t) = 32t^3 - 48t^2 + 18t - 1, \\ T_4^*(t) = 128t^4 - 256t^3 + 160t^2 - 32t + 1, T_5^*(t) = 512t^5 - 1280t^4 + 1120t^3 - 400t^2 + 46t - 1.$$

$$y(t) = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1(2t - 1) + \alpha_2(8t^2 - 8t + 1) + \alpha_3(32t^3 - 48t^2 + 18t - 1) + \alpha_4(128t^4 - 256t^3 + 160t^2 - 32t + 1) + \alpha_5(512t^5 - 1280t^4 + 1120t^3 - 400t^2 + 46t - 1).$$

$y(s) = \sum_{i=1}^5 \alpha_i T_i^*(s)$, where,

$$T_0^*(s) = 1, T_1^*(s) = 2s - 1, T_2^*(s) = 8s^2 - 8s + 1, T_3^*(s) = 32s^3 - 48s^2 + 18s - 1, \\ T_4^*(s) = 128s^4 - 256s^3 + 160s^2 - 32s + 1, \\ T_5^*(s) = 512s^5 - 1280s^4 + 1120s^3 - 400s^2 + 46s - 1.$$

$$y(s) = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1(2s - 1) + \alpha_2(8s^2 - 8s + 1) + \alpha_3(32s^3 - 48s^2 + 18s - 1) + \alpha_4(128s^4 - 256s^3 + 160s^2 - 32s + 1) + \alpha_5(512s^5 - 1280s^4 + 1120s^3 - 400s^2 + 46s - 1).$$

Consider the Volterra integral equation

$$y(t) = f(t) + \int_0^t a(t, s)y(s)ds, \quad t \geq 0. \quad (17)$$

Substituting the values of $y(t)$ and $y(s)$ into the equation gives;

$$\sum_{i=1}^5 \alpha_i T_i^*(t) = f(t) + \int_0^t a(t, s) \sum_{i=1}^5 \alpha_i T_i^*(s) ds$$

Which can be expanded to get

$$\alpha_0 + \alpha_1(2t - 1) + \alpha_2(8t^2 - 8t + 1) + \alpha_3(32t^3 - 48t^2 + 18t - 1) + \alpha_4(128t^4 - 256t^3 + 160t^2 - 32t + 1) + \alpha_5(512t^5 + 1280t^4 + 1120t^3 - 400t^2 + 46t - 1) = f(t) + \int_0^t a(t, s) [\alpha_0 + \alpha_1(2s - 1) + \alpha_2(8s^2 - 8s + 1) + \alpha_3(32s^3 - 48s^2 + 18s - 1) + \alpha_4(128s^4 - 256s^3 + 160s^2 - 32s + 1) + \alpha_5(512s^5 + 1280s^4 + 1120s^3 - 400s^2 + 46s - 1)] ds$$

$$\alpha_0 + 2\alpha_1 t - \alpha_1 + 8\alpha_2 t^2 - 8\alpha_2 t + \alpha_2 + 32\alpha_3 t^3 - 48\alpha_3 t^2 + 18\alpha_3 t - \alpha_3 + 128\alpha_4 t^4 - 256\alpha_4 t^3 + 160\alpha_4 t^2 - 32\alpha_4 t + \alpha_4 + 512\alpha_5 t^5 - 1280\alpha_5 t^4 + 1120\alpha_5 t^3 - 400\alpha_5 t^2 + 46\alpha_5 t - \alpha_5 = f(t) + \int_0^t a(t, s) [\alpha_0 + \alpha_1(2s - 1) + \alpha_2(8s^2 - 8s + 1) + \alpha_3(32s^3 - 48s^2 + 18s - 1) + \alpha_4(128s^4 - 256s^3 + 160s^2 - 32s + 1) + \alpha_5(512s^5 + 1280s^4 + 1120s^3 - 400s^2 + 46s - 1)] ds$$

$$\alpha_0 + 2\alpha_1 t - \alpha_1 + 8\alpha_2 t^2 - 8\alpha_2 t + \alpha_2 + 32\alpha_3 t^3 - 48\alpha_3 t^2 + 18\alpha_3 t - \alpha_3 + 128\alpha_4 t^4 - 256\alpha_4 t^3 + 160\alpha_4 t^2 - 32\alpha_4 t + \alpha_4 + 512\alpha_5 t^5 - 1280\alpha_5 t^4 + 1120\alpha_5 t^3 - 400\alpha_5 t^2 + 46\alpha_5 t - \alpha_5 - \left(\int_0^t a(t, s) [\alpha_0 + \alpha_1(2s - 1) + \alpha_2(8s^2 - 8s + 1) + \alpha_3(32s^3 - 48s^2 + 18s - 1) + \alpha_4(128s^4 - 256s^3 + 160s^2 - 32s + 1) + \alpha_5(512s^5 + 1280s^4 + 1120s^3 - 400s^2 + 46s - 1)] ds \right) = f(t).$$

For source function $f(t)$ polynomial truncated at degree 5

$$\alpha_0 + 2\alpha_1 t - \alpha_1 + 8\alpha_2 t^2 - 8\alpha_2 t + \alpha_2 + 32\alpha_3 t^3 - 48\alpha_3 t^2 + 18\alpha_3 t - \alpha_3 + 128\alpha_4 t^4 - 256\alpha_4 t^3 + 160\alpha_4 t^2 - 32\alpha_4 t + \alpha_4 + 512\alpha_5 t^5 - 1280\alpha_5 t^4 + 1120\alpha_5 t^3 - 400\alpha_5 t^2 + 46\alpha_5 t - \alpha_5 - \left(\int_0^t a(t, s) [\alpha_0 + \alpha_1(2s - 1) + \alpha_2(8s^2 - 8s + 1) + \alpha_3(32s^3 - 48s^2 + 18s - 1) + \alpha_4(128s^4 - 256s^3 + 160s^2 - 32s + 1) + \alpha_5(512s^5 + 1280s^4 + 1120s^3 - 400s^2 + 46s - 1)] ds \right) = a_0 + a_1 t + a_2 t^2 + \dots + a_5 t^5.$$

Substituting the kernel and comparing the coefficients of t on both sides leads to a system of algebraic equation that can be solved easily to get the values of α and the solution of the integral equation.

4 RESULT AND ANALYSIS

4.1 Numerical Experiments

4.1.1 Example 1

Solve for $f(x)$ in the Volterra integral equation given by

$$f(x) = 1 + \int_0^x f(t)dt,$$

Using the shifted Chebyshev collocation method

Let

$$f(x) = \sum_{i=0}^n \alpha_i T_i^*(x),$$

using $n = 4$;

$$f(x) = \sum_{i=0}^4 \alpha_i T_i^*(x),$$

where,

$$T_0^*(x) = 1, T_1^*(x) = 2x - 1, T_2^*(x) = 8x^2 - 8x + 1, T_3^*(x) = 32x^3 - 48x^2 + 18x - 1, T_4^*(x) = 128x^4 - 256x^3 + 160x^2 - 32x + 1.$$

$$f(x) = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1(2x - 1) + \alpha_2(8x^2 - 8x + 1) + \alpha_3(32x^3 - 48x^2 + 18x - 1) + \alpha_4(128x^4 - 256x^3 + 160x^2 - 32x + 1).$$

$$f(t) = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1(2t - 1) + \alpha_2(8t^2 - 8t + 1) + \alpha_3(32t^3 - 48t^2 + 18t - 1) + \alpha_4(128t^4 - 256t^3 + 160t^2 - 32t + 1).$$

Putting these into the equation given

$$\alpha_0 + \alpha_1(2x - 1) + \alpha_2(8x^2 - 8x + 1) + \alpha_3(32x^3 - 48x^2 + 18x - 1) + \alpha_4(128x^4 - 256x^3 + 160x^2 - 32x + 1) = 1 + \int_0^x \alpha_0 + \alpha_1(2t - 1) + \alpha_2(8t^2 - 8t + 1) + \alpha_3(32t^3 -$$

$$48t^2 + 18t - 1) + \alpha_4(128t^4 - 256t^3 + 160t^2 - 32t + 1)dt$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \alpha_0 + 2\alpha_1x - \alpha_1 + 8\alpha_2x^2 - 8\alpha_2x + \alpha_2 + 32\alpha_3x^3 - 48\alpha_3x^2 + 18\alpha_3x - \alpha_3 + 128\alpha_4x^4 \\ & - 256\alpha_4x^3 + 160\alpha_4x^2 - 32\alpha_4x + \alpha_4 = 1 + \int_0^x [\alpha_0 + \alpha_1(2t - 1) + \alpha_2(8t^2 - 8t + 1) + \\ & \alpha_3(32t^3 - 48t^2 + 18t - 1) + \alpha_4(128t^4 - 256t^3 + 160t^2 - 32t + 1)] dt \end{aligned}$$

Taking the integral

$$\begin{aligned} & \alpha_0 + 2\alpha_1x - \alpha_1 + 8\alpha_2x^2 - 8\alpha_2x + \alpha_2 + 32\alpha_3x^3 - 48\alpha_3x^2 + 18\alpha_3x - \alpha_3 + 128\alpha_4x^4 \\ & - 256\alpha_4x^3 + 160\alpha_4x^2 - 32\alpha_4x + \alpha_4 = 1 + [\alpha_0t + \alpha_1(t^2 - t) + \alpha_2(\frac{8t^3}{3} - 4t^2 + t) + \alpha_3(8t^4 - \\ & 16t^3 + 9t^2 - t) + \alpha_4(\frac{128t^5}{5} - 64t^4 + \frac{160t^3}{3} - 16t^2 + t)]_0^x \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \alpha_0 + 2\alpha_1x - \alpha_1 + 8\alpha_2x^2 - 8\alpha_2x + \alpha_2 + 32\alpha_3x^3 - 48\alpha_3x^2 + 18\alpha_3x - \alpha_3 + 128\alpha_4x^4 \\ & - 256\alpha_4x^3 + 160\alpha_4x^2 - 32\alpha_4x + \alpha_4 = 1 + \alpha_0x + \alpha_1(x^2 - x) + \alpha_2(\frac{8x^3}{3} - 4x^2 + x) + \\ & \alpha_3(8x^4 - 16x^3 + 9x^2 - x) + \alpha_4(\frac{128x^5}{5} - 64x^4 + \frac{160x^3}{3} - 16x^2 + x) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \alpha_0 + 2\alpha_1x - \alpha_1 + 8\alpha_2x^2 - 8\alpha_2x + \alpha_2 + 32\alpha_3x^3 - 48\alpha_3x^2 + 18\alpha_3x - \alpha_3 + 128\alpha_4x^4 \\ & - 256\alpha_4x^3 + 160\alpha_4x^2 - 32\alpha_4x + \alpha_4 = 1 + \alpha_0x + \alpha_1x^2 - \alpha_1x + \frac{8x^3\alpha_2}{3} - 4\alpha_2x^2 + \alpha_2x + \\ & 8\alpha_3x^4 - 16\alpha_3x^3 + 9\alpha_3x^2 - \alpha_3x + \frac{128x^5\alpha_4}{5} - 64\alpha_4x^4 + \frac{160x^3\alpha_4}{3} - 16\alpha_4x^2 + \alpha_4x \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \alpha_0 + 2\alpha_1x - \alpha_1 + 8\alpha_2x^2 - 8\alpha_2x + \alpha_2 + 32\alpha_3x^3 - 48\alpha_3x^2 + 18\alpha_3x - \alpha_3 + 128\alpha_4x^4 \\ & - 256\alpha_4x^3 + 160\alpha_4x^2 - 32\alpha_4x + \alpha_4 - [\alpha_0x + \alpha_1x^2 - \alpha_1x + \frac{8x^3\alpha_2}{3} - 4\alpha_2x^2 + \alpha_2x + 8\alpha_3x^4 - \\ & 16\alpha_3x^3 + 9\alpha_3x^2 - \alpha_3x + \frac{128x^5\alpha_4}{5} - 64\alpha_4x^4 + \frac{160x^3\alpha_4}{3} - 16\alpha_4x^2 + \alpha_4x] = 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \alpha_0 + 2\alpha_1x - \alpha_1 + 8\alpha_2x^2 - 8\alpha_2x + \alpha_2 + 32\alpha_3x^3 - 48\alpha_3x^2 + 18\alpha_3x - \alpha_3 + 128\alpha_4x^4 \\ & - 256\alpha_4x^3 + 160\alpha_4x^2 - 32\alpha_4x + \alpha_4 - \alpha_0x - \alpha_1x^2 + \alpha_1x - \frac{8x^3\alpha_2}{3} + 4\alpha_2x^2 - \alpha_2x - 8\alpha_3x^4 + \\ & 16\alpha_3x^3 - 9\alpha_3x^2 + \alpha_3x - \frac{128x^5\alpha_4}{5} + 64\alpha_4x^4 - \frac{160x^3\alpha_4}{3} + 16\alpha_4x^2 - \alpha_4x = 1 \end{aligned}$$

Collecting like terms

$$\begin{aligned} & \alpha_0 - \alpha_1 + \alpha_2 - \alpha_3 + \alpha_4 + [-\alpha_0 + 3\alpha_1 - 7\alpha_2 + 19\alpha_3 - 33\alpha_4]x + [-\alpha_1 + 12\alpha_2 - \\ & 57\alpha_3 + 176\alpha_4]x^2 + [-\frac{8\alpha_2}{3} + 32\alpha_3 + 16\alpha_3 - 256\alpha_4 - \frac{160\alpha_4}{3}]x^3 + [-16\alpha_3 + 192\alpha_4]x^4 = 1 \end{aligned}$$

Comparing both sides

$$\alpha_0 - \alpha_1 + \alpha_2 - \alpha_3 + \alpha_4 = 1$$

$$- \alpha_0 + 3\alpha_1 - 7\alpha_2 + 19\alpha_3 - 33\alpha_4 = 0$$

$$- \alpha_1 + 12\alpha_2 - 57\alpha_3 + 176\alpha_4 = 0$$

$$-\frac{8\alpha_2}{3} + 48\alpha_3 - \frac{928\alpha_4}{3} = 0$$

$$- 16\alpha_3 + 192\alpha_4 = 0$$

Solving this system of equations for α

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & -1 & 1 & -1 & 1 \\ -1 & 3 & -7 & 19 & -33 \\ 0 & -1 & 12 & -57 & 176 \\ 0 & 0 & -\frac{8}{3} & 48 & -\frac{928}{3} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -16 & 192 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \alpha_0 \\ \alpha_1 \\ \alpha_2 \\ \alpha_3 \\ \alpha_4 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

The augmented matrix

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & -1 & 1 & -1 & 1 & 1 \\ -1 & 3 & -7 & 19 & -33 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 12 & -57 & 176 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -\frac{8}{3} & 48 & -\frac{928}{3} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -16 & 192 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

Reducing the augmented matrix gives

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1.60406404 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.63793103 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0.02709360 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & -0.00738916 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & -0.00061576 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\alpha_0 = 1.60406404, \alpha_1 = 0.63793103, \alpha_2 = 0.02709360, \alpha_3 = -0.00738916, \alpha_4 = -0.00061576.$$

$$\begin{aligned}
f(x) &= \alpha_0 + \alpha_1(2x - 1) + \alpha_2(8x^2 - 8x + 1) + \alpha_3(32x^3 - 48x^2 + 18x - 1) + \alpha_4(128x^4 - 256x^3 + 160x^2 - 32x + 1) \\
&= 1.60406404 + 0.63793103(2x + 1) + 0.02709360(8x^2 - 8x + 1) - 0.00738916(32x^3 - 48x^2 + 18x - 1) - 0.00061576(128x^4 - 256x^3 + 160x^2 - 32x + 1) \\
&= 1.60406404 + 1.27586206x - 0.63793103 + 0.2167488x^2 - 0.2167488x + 0.02709360 - 0.23645312x^3 + 0.35467968x^2 - 0.13300488x + 0.00738916 - 0.07881728x^4 + 0.15763456x^3 - 0.0985216x^2 + 0.01970432x - 0.00061576 \\
&= 1.60406404 - 0.63793103 + 0.02709360 + 0.00738916 - 0.00061576 + [1.27586206 - 0.2167488 - 0.13300488 + 0.01970432]x + [0.2167488 + 0.35467968 - 0.0985216]x^2 + [-0.23645312 + 0.15763456]x^3 - 0.07881728x^4 \\
&= 1.00000001 + 0.9458127x + 0.47290688x^2 - 0.07881856x^3 - 0.07881728x^4
\end{aligned}$$

For comparison, exact solution, $f(x) = e^x$

t	Exact Solution	Approximate Solution	Error = $\ Exact - Analytic\ $
0	1	1.00000001	0.00000001
0.25	1.28402542	1.28447045	0.00044503
0.5	1.64872127	1.64856354	0.00015773
0.75	2.11700002	2.11791717	0.00091715
1.0	2.71828183	2.71826108	0.00002075

Table 4.1: Comparison of the exact and approximate solutions of example 1

4.1.2 Example 2

Consider the Volterra integral equation of the second kind

$$u(x) = 6x - 3x^2 + \int_0^x u(t)dt,$$

To solve this using shifted Chebyshev collocation method

Let

$$u(x) = \sum_{i=0}^n \alpha_i T_i^*(x),$$

using $n = 4$;

$$y(x) = \sum_{i=0}^4 \alpha_i T_i^*(x),$$

where,

$$T_0^*(x) = 1, T_1^*(x) = 2x - 1, T_2^*(x) = 8x^2 - 8x + 1, T_3^*(x) = 32x^3 - 48x^2 + 18x - 1, T_4^*(x) = 128x^4 - 256x^3 + 160x^2 - 32x + 1.$$

$$u(x) = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1(2x - 1) + \alpha_2(8x^2 - 8x + 1) + \alpha_3(32x^3 - 48x^2 + 18x - 1) + \alpha_4(128x^4 - 256x^3 + 160x^2 - 32x + 1).$$

$$u(t) = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1(2t - 1) + \alpha_2(8t^2 - 8t + 1) + \alpha_3(32t^3 - 48t^2 + 18t - 1) + \alpha_4(128t^4 - 256t^3 + 160t^2 - 32t + 1).$$

Putting these into the equation given

$$\alpha_0 + \alpha_1(2x - 1) + \alpha_2(8x^2 - 8x + 1) + \alpha_3(32x^3 - 48x^2 + 18x - 1) + \alpha_4(128x^4 - 256x^3 + 160x^2 - 32x + 1) - \int_0^x \alpha_0 + \alpha_1(2t - 1) + \alpha_2(8t^2 - 8t + 1) + \alpha_3(32t^3 - 48t^2 + 18t - 1) + \alpha_4(128t^4 - 256t^3 + 160t^2 - 32t + 1)dt = 6x - 3x^2$$

$$\alpha_0 + 2\alpha_1x - \alpha_1 + 8\alpha_2x^2 - 8\alpha_2x + \alpha_2 + 32\alpha_3x^3 - 48\alpha_3x^2 + 18\alpha_3x - \alpha_3 + 128\alpha_4x^4 - 256\alpha_4x^3 + 160\alpha_4x^2 - 32\alpha_4x + \alpha_4 - [\alpha_0t + \alpha_1(t^2 - t) + \alpha_2(\frac{8t^3}{3} - 4t^2 + t) + \alpha_3(8t^4 -$$

$$16t^3 + 9t^2 - t) + \alpha_4(\frac{128t^5}{5} - 64t^4 + \frac{160t^3}{3} - 16t^2 + t)]_0^x = 6x - 3x^2$$

Substituting the integral bounds

$$\begin{aligned} & \alpha_0 + 2\alpha_1x - \alpha_1 + 8\alpha_2x^2 - 8\alpha_2x + \alpha_2 + 32\alpha_3x^3 - 48\alpha_3x^2 + 18\alpha_3x - \alpha_3 + 128\alpha_4x^4 \\ & - 256\alpha_4x^3 + 160\alpha_4x^2 - 32\alpha_4x + \alpha_4 - [\alpha_0x + \alpha_1(x^2 - x) + \alpha_2(\frac{8x^3}{3} - 4x^2 + x) + \alpha_3(8x^4 - \\ & 16x^3 + 9x^2 - x) + \alpha_4(\frac{128x^5}{5} - 64x^4 + \frac{160x^3}{3} - 16x^2 + x)] = 6x - 3x^2 \end{aligned}$$

Expanding the brackets

$$\begin{aligned} & \alpha_0 + 2\alpha_1x - \alpha_1 + 8\alpha_2x^2 - 8\alpha_2x + \alpha_2 + 32\alpha_3x^3 - 48\alpha_3x^2 + 18\alpha_3x - \alpha_3 + 128\alpha_4x^4 \\ & - 256\alpha_4x^3 + 160\alpha_4x^2 - 32\alpha_4x + \alpha_4 - [\alpha_0x + \alpha_1x^2 - \alpha_1x + \frac{8x^3\alpha_2}{3} - 4\alpha_2x^2 + \alpha_2x + 8\alpha_3x^4 - \\ & 16\alpha_3x^3 + 9\alpha_3x^2 - \alpha_3x + \frac{128x^5\alpha_4}{5} - 64\alpha_4x^4 + \frac{160x^3\alpha_4}{3} - 16\alpha_4x^2 + \alpha_4x] = 6x - 3x^2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \alpha_0 + 2\alpha_1x - \alpha_1 + 8\alpha_2x^2 - 8\alpha_2x + \alpha_2 + 32\alpha_3x^3 - 48\alpha_3x^2 + 18\alpha_3x - \alpha_3 + 128\alpha_4x^4 \\ & - 256\alpha_4x^3 + 160\alpha_4x^2 - 32\alpha_4x + \alpha_4 - \alpha_0x - \alpha_1x^2 + \alpha_1x - \frac{8x^3\alpha_2}{3} + 4\alpha_2x^2 - \alpha_2x - 8\alpha_3x^4 + \\ & 16\alpha_3x^3 - 9\alpha_3x^2 + \alpha_3x - \frac{128x^5\alpha_4}{5} + 64\alpha_4x^4 - \frac{160x^3\alpha_4}{3} + 16\alpha_4x^2 - \alpha_4x = 6x - 3x^2 \end{aligned}$$

Collecting like terms

$$\begin{aligned} & \alpha_0 - \alpha_1 + \alpha_2 - \alpha_3 + \alpha_4 + [-\alpha_0 + 2\alpha_1 + \alpha_1 - 8\alpha_2 - \alpha_2 + 18\alpha_3 + \alpha_3 - 32\alpha_4 - \alpha_4]x \\ & + [-\alpha_1 + 8\alpha_2 + 4\alpha_2 - 48\alpha_3 - 9\alpha_3 + 160\alpha_4 + 16\alpha_4]x^2 + [-\frac{8\alpha_2}{3} + 32\alpha_3 + 16\alpha_3 - 256\alpha_4 \\ & - \frac{160\alpha_4}{3}]x^3 + [-8\alpha_3 - 8\alpha_3 + 128\alpha_4 + 64\alpha_4]x^4 = 6x - 3x^2 \end{aligned}$$

Comparing both sides

$$\begin{aligned} & \alpha_0 - \alpha_1 + \alpha_2 - \alpha_3 + \alpha_4 = 0 \\ & -\alpha_0 + 3\alpha_1 - 7\alpha_2 + 19\alpha_3 - 33\alpha_4 = 6 \\ & -\alpha_1 + 12\alpha_2 - 57\alpha_3 + 176\alpha_4 = -3 \\ & -\frac{8\alpha_2}{3} + 48\alpha_3 - \frac{928\alpha_4}{3} = 0 \\ & -16\alpha_3 + 192\alpha_4 = 0 \end{aligned}$$

Solving this system of equations for α

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & -1 & 1 & -1 & 1 \\ -1 & 3 & -7 & 19 & -33 \\ 0 & -1 & 12 & -57 & 176 \\ 0 & 0 & -\frac{8}{3} & 48 & -\frac{928}{3} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -16 & 192 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \alpha_0 \\ \alpha_1 \\ \alpha_2 \\ \alpha_3 \\ \alpha_4 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 6 \\ -3 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

The augmented matrix

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & -1 & 1 & -1 & 1 & 0 \\ -1 & 3 & -7 & 19 & -33 & 6 \\ 0 & -1 & 12 & -57 & 176 & -3 \\ 0 & 0 & -\frac{8}{3} & 48 & -\frac{928}{3} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -16 & 192 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

Reducing the augmented matrix gives

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -4.24877 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -4.65517 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & -0.32512 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0.08867 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0.00739 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\alpha_0 = -4.24877, \alpha_1 = -4.65517, \alpha_2 = -0.32512, \alpha_3 = 0.08867, \alpha_4 = 0.00739.$$

$$u(x) = -4.24877 - 4.65517(2x - 1) - 0.32512(8x^2 - 8x + 1) + 0.08867(32x^3 - 48x^2 + 18x - 1) + 0.00739(128x^4 - 256x^3 + 160x^2 - 32x + 1)$$

$$u(x) = 0.94592x^4 + 0.9456x^3 - 5.67472x^2 - 5.3498x + 0.01.$$

4.2 Industrial Applications

4.2.1 The Maxwell Model

The Maxwell model is a series connection of a spring and dashpot.

Figure 1: Maxwell model

In this model ϵ_D and σ_D denote the strain and stress in the spring alone, and ϵ_D, σ_D denote those in the dashpot alone. The total stress is given by $\sigma = \sigma_S = \sigma_D$ and the total strain by $\epsilon = \epsilon_S + \epsilon_D$. Differentiating and using Hooke's and Newton's laws yield

$$\frac{d\epsilon}{dt} = \frac{d\sigma_S}{E dt} + \frac{\sigma_D}{\eta} \Rightarrow \frac{d\sigma}{dt} + \frac{\sigma}{\tau} = E \frac{d\epsilon}{dt}, \quad (18)$$

Where $\tau := \frac{\eta}{E}$ is the relaxation time. Using $\sigma(0) = E\epsilon(0)$ this Ordinary Differential Equation (ODE) is easily solved to give

$$\sigma(t) = E e^{-\frac{t}{\tau}} \epsilon(0) + E \int_0^t e^{-(t-s)\tau} \epsilon'(s) ds. \quad (19)$$

4.2.2 The Voigt Model

Connecting the spring and dashpot in parallel yields the Voigt model. This time $\epsilon = \epsilon_S + \epsilon_D$ and equilibrium demands that $\sigma = \sigma_S = \sigma_D$, hence

Figure 2: Voigt model

$$\eta \frac{d\epsilon}{dt} + E\epsilon = \sigma \Rightarrow \frac{d\epsilon}{dt} + \frac{\epsilon}{\tau} = \frac{\sigma}{\eta}. \quad (20)$$

This gives the constitutive law in hereditary form as

$$\epsilon(t) = e^{-\frac{t}{\tau}}\epsilon(0) + \frac{1}{\eta} \int_0^t e^{-(t-s)\tau} \sigma(s) ds. \quad (21)$$

4.2.3 The Linear Convolution Volterra Model

The hereditary nature of the constitutive equations gives rise to integral equations and more generally functional differential equations, attention is confined here to the quasi-static bending of linear viscoelastic rods: inertia, shear and twist are ignored. The linear non-convolution Volterra equation model is satisfied by the modes of a

viscoelastic rod bending quasistatically, the Volterra Integral Equation (VIE);

$$y(t) = f(t) + \int_0^t \frac{k(t-s)}{1-p(t)} y(s) ds, \quad t \geq 0, \quad (22)$$

With $0 \leq p(t)$, $k(z) > 0$ and $\int_0^\infty k(z) dz < 1$.

Let $a(t,s) = \frac{k(t-s)}{1-p(t)}$, equation (20) turns:

$$y(t) = f(t) + \int_0^t a(t,s)y(s)ds, \quad t \geq 0. \quad (23)$$

4.3 Analytic Solution

Recall that $y(t) = f(t) + \int_0^t \frac{k(t-s)}{1-p(t)} y(s) ds$ and

$$y(t) = f(t) + \int_0^t a(t,s)y(s)ds, \text{ where } a(t,s) = \frac{k(t-s)}{1-p(t)}.$$

For the model of a viscoelastic rod bending quasi statically the values of $a(t,s)$ is given as $a(t,s) = t + 6(t-s) - 4(t-s)^2$ and $f(t) = -2 - t - 4t^2$.

Putting these into

$$\alpha_0 + 2\alpha_1 t - \alpha_1 + 8\alpha_2 t^2 - 8\alpha_2 t + \alpha_2 + 32\alpha_3 t^3 - 48\alpha_3 t^2 + 18\alpha_3 t - \alpha_3 + 128\alpha_4 t^4 - 256\alpha_4 t^3 + 160\alpha_4 t^2 - 32\alpha_4 t + \alpha_4 + 512\alpha_5 t^5 - 1280\alpha_5 t^4 + 1120\alpha_5 t^3 - 400\alpha_5 t^2 + 46\alpha_5 t - \alpha_5 - \left(\int_0^t a(t,s) [\alpha_0 + \alpha_1(2s-1) + \alpha_2(8s^2-8s+1) + \alpha_3(32s^3-48s^2+18s-1) + \alpha_4(128s^4-256s^3+160s^2-32s+1) + \alpha_5(512s^5+1280s^4+1120s^3-400s^2+46s-1)] ds \right) = f(t), \text{ gives}$$

$$\alpha_0 + 2\alpha_1 t - \alpha_1 + 8\alpha_2 t^2 - 8\alpha_2 t + \alpha_2 + 32\alpha_3 t^3 - 48\alpha_3 t^2 + 18\alpha_3 t - \alpha_3 + 128\alpha_4 t^4 - 256\alpha_4 t^3 + 160\alpha_4 t^2 - 32\alpha_4 t + \alpha_4 + 512\alpha_5 t^5 - 1280\alpha_5 t^4 + 1120\alpha_5 t^3 - 400\alpha_5 t^2 + 46\alpha_5 t - \alpha_5 - \left(\int_0^t (t + 6(t-s) - 4(t-s)^2) [\alpha_0 + \alpha_1(2s-1) + \alpha_2(8s^2-8s+1) + \alpha_3(32s^3-48s^2+18s-1) + \alpha_4(128s^4-256s^3+160s^2-32s+1) + \alpha_5(512s^5+1280s^4+1120s^3-400s^2+46s-1)] ds \right) = -2 - t - 4t^2$$

Expanding this gives

$$\alpha_0 + 2\alpha_1 t - \alpha_1 + 8\alpha_2 t^2 - 8\alpha_2 t + \alpha_2 + 32\alpha_3 t^3 - 48\alpha_3 t^2 + 18\alpha_3 t - \alpha_3 + 128\alpha_4 t^4 - 256\alpha_4 t^3 + 160\alpha_4 t^2 - 32\alpha_4 t + \alpha_4 + 512\alpha_5 t^5 - 1280\alpha_5 t^4 + 1120\alpha_5 t^3 - 400\alpha_5 t^2 + 46\alpha_5 t - \alpha_5 - \left(\int_0^t (7t - 6s + 8st - 4t^2 - 4s^2)[\alpha_0 + \alpha_1(2s - 1) + \alpha_2(8s^2 - 8s + 1) + \alpha_3(32s^3 - 48s^2 + 18s - 1) + \alpha_4(128s^4 - 256s^3 + 160s^2 - 32s + 1) + \alpha_5(512s^5 + 1280s^4 + 1120s^3 - 400s^2 + 46s - 1)] ds\right) = -2 - t - 4t^2$$

$$\alpha_0 + 2\alpha_1 t - \alpha_1 + 8\alpha_2 t^2 - 8\alpha_2 t + \alpha_2 + 32\alpha_3 t^3 - 48\alpha_3 t^2 + 18\alpha_3 t - \alpha_3 + 128\alpha_4 t^4 - 256\alpha_4 t^3 + 160\alpha_4 t^2 - 32\alpha_4 t + \alpha_4 + 512\alpha_5 t^5 - 1280\alpha_5 t^4 + 1120\alpha_5 t^3 - 400\alpha_5 t^2 + 46\alpha_5 t - \alpha_5 - \left[\left(\int_0^t (7t\alpha_0 + 7t\alpha_1(2s-1) + 7t\alpha_2(8s^2 - 8s + 1) + 7t\alpha_3(32s^3 - 48s^2 + 18s - 1) + 7t\alpha_4(128s^4 - 256s^3 + 160s^2 - 32s + 1) + 7t\alpha_5(512s^5 + 1280s^4 + 1120s^3 - 400s^2 + 46s - 1)) - [6s\alpha_0 + 6\alpha_1(2s^2 - s) + 6\alpha_2(8s^3 - 8s^2 + s) + 6\alpha_3(32s^4 - 48s^3 + 18s^2 - s) + 6\alpha_4(128s^5 - 256s^4 + 160s^3 - 32s^2 + s) + 6\alpha_5(512s^6 - 1280s^5 + 1120s^4 - 400s^3 + 46s^2 - s)] + [8st\alpha_0 + 8t\alpha_1(2s^2 - s) + 8t\alpha_2(8s^3 - 8s^2 + s) + 8t\alpha_3(32s^4 - 48s^3 + 18s^2 - s) + 8t\alpha_4(128s^5 - 256s^4 + 160s^3 - 32s^2 + s) + 8t\alpha_5(512s^6 - 1280s^5 + 1120s^4 - 400s^3 + 46s^2 - s)] - [4t^2\alpha_0 + 4t^2\alpha_1(2s-1) + 4t^2\alpha_2(8s^2 - 8s + 1) + 4t^2\alpha_3(32s^3 - 48s^2 + 18s - 1) + 4t^2\alpha_4(128s^4 - 256s^3 + 160s^2 - 32s + 1) + 4t^2\alpha_5(512s^5 + 1280s^4 + 1120s^3 - 400s^2 + 46s - 1)] - [4s^2\alpha_0 + 4\alpha_1(2s^3 - s^2) + 4\alpha_2(8s^4 - 8s^3 + s^2) + 4\alpha_3(32s^5 - 48s^4 + 18s^3 - s^2) + 4\alpha_4(128s^6 - 256s^5 + 160s^4 - 32s^3 + s^2) + 4\alpha_5(512s^7 - 1280s^6 + 1120s^5 - 400s^4 + 46s^3 - s^2)]\right) ds = -2 - t - 4t^2.$$

Integrating with respect to s,

$$\alpha_0 + 2\alpha_1 t - \alpha_1 + 8\alpha_2 t^2 - 8\alpha_2 t + \alpha_2 + 32\alpha_3 t^3 - 48\alpha_3 t^2 + 18\alpha_3 t - \alpha_3 + 128\alpha_4 t^4 - 256\alpha_4 t^3 + 160\alpha_4 t^2 - 32\alpha_4 t + \alpha_4 + 512\alpha_5 t^5 - 1280\alpha_5 t^4 + 1120\alpha_5 t^3 - 400\alpha_5 t^2 + 46\alpha_5 t - \alpha_5 - \left[\left[(7st\alpha_0 + 7t\alpha_1(s^2 - s) + 7t\alpha_2\left(\frac{8s^3}{3} - 4s^2 + s\right) + 7t\alpha_3(8s^4 - 16s^3 + 9s^2 - s) + 7t\alpha_4\left(\frac{128s^5}{5} - 64s^4 + 160s^3 - 16s^2 + s\right) + 7t\alpha_5\left(\frac{512s^6}{6} + 256s^5 + 280s^4 - 400s^3 - 23s^2 - s\right)\right] - [3s^2\alpha_0 + 6\alpha_1\left(\frac{2s^3}{3} - \frac{s^2}{2}\right) + 6\alpha_2\left(2s^4 - \frac{8s^3}{3} + \frac{s^2}{2}\right) + 6\alpha_3\left(\frac{32s^5}{5} - 12s^4 + 6s^3 - \frac{s^2}{2}\right) + 6\alpha_4\left(\frac{128s^6}{6} - \frac{256s^5}{5} + 40s^4 - \frac{32s^3}{3} + \frac{s^2}{2}\right) + 6\alpha_5\left(\frac{512s^7}{7} - \frac{1280s^6}{6} + 224s^5 - 100s^4 + 46s^3 - \frac{s^2}{2}\right)] + [4s^2t\alpha_0 + 8t\alpha_1\left(\frac{2s^3}{3} - \frac{s^2}{2}\right) + 8t\alpha_2\left(2s^4 - \frac{8s^3}{3} + \frac{s^2}{2}\right) + 8t\alpha_3\left(\frac{32s^5}{5} - 12s^4 + 6s^3 - \frac{s^2}{2}\right) + 8t\alpha_4\left(\frac{128s^6}{6} - \frac{256s^5}{5} + 40s^4 - \frac{32s^3}{3} + \frac{s^2}{2}\right) + \right.$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 8t\alpha_5\left(\frac{512s^7}{7}-\frac{1280s^6}{6}+224s^5-100s^4+\frac{46s^3}{3}-\frac{s^2}{2}\right)] - [(4st^2\alpha_0 + 4t^2\alpha_1(s^2-s)+4t^2\alpha_2\left(\frac{8s^3}{3}-4s^2+s\right) \\
& + 4t^2\alpha_3(8s^4-16s^3+9s^2-s)+4t^2\alpha_4\left(\frac{128s^5}{5}-64s^4+\frac{160s^3}{3}-16s^2+s\right)+4t^2\alpha_5\left(\frac{512s^6}{6}+256s^5+ \\
& 280s^4-\frac{400s^3}{3}+23s^2-s\right)] - \left[\frac{4s^3}{3}\alpha_0 + 4\alpha_1\left(\frac{s^4}{2}-\frac{s^3}{3}\right)+4\alpha_2\left(\frac{8s^5}{5}-2s^4+\frac{s^3}{3}\right)+4\alpha_3\left(\frac{32s^6}{6}-\frac{48s^5}{5}+\frac{18s^4}{4}-\right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. \frac{s^3}{3}+4\alpha_4\left(\frac{128s^7}{7}-\frac{256s^6}{6}+32s^5-8s^4-\frac{s^3}{3}\right)+4\alpha_5\left(64s^8-\frac{1280s^7}{7}+\frac{1120s^6}{6}-80s^5+\frac{46s^4}{4}-\frac{s^3}{3}\right)\right]ds \Big|_0^t = -2t-4t^2.
\end{aligned}$$

Substituting the integral bounds,

$$\begin{aligned}
& \alpha_0 + 2\alpha_1t - \alpha_1 + 8\alpha_2t^2 - 8\alpha_2t + \alpha_2 + 32\alpha_3t^3 - 48\alpha_3t^2 + 18\alpha_3t - \alpha_3 + 128\alpha_4t^4 - \\
& 256\alpha_4t^3 + 160\alpha_4t^2 - 32\alpha_4t + \alpha_4 + 512\alpha_5t^5 - 1280\alpha_5t^4 + 1120\alpha_5t^3 - 400\alpha_5t^2 + 46\alpha_5t \\
& - \alpha_5 - [(7t^2\alpha_0 + 7t\alpha_1(t^2-t) + 7t\alpha_2\left(\frac{8t^3}{3}-4t^2+t\right) + 7t\alpha_3(8t^4-16t^3+9t^2-t) + \\
& 7t\alpha_4\left(\frac{128t^5}{5}-64t^4+\frac{160t^3}{3}-16t^2+t\right) + 7t\alpha_5\left(\frac{512t^6}{6}+256t^5+280t^4-\frac{400t^3}{3}+23t^2-t\right)- \\
& [3t^2\alpha_0 + 6\alpha_1\left(\frac{2t^3}{3}-\frac{t^2}{2}\right) + 6\alpha_2\left(2t^4-\frac{8t^3}{3}+\frac{t^2}{2}\right) + 6\alpha_3\left(\frac{32t^5}{5}-12t^4+6t^3-\frac{t^2}{2}\right) + 6\alpha_4\left(\frac{128t^6}{6}-\frac{256t^5}{5}+ \\
& 40t^4-\frac{32t^3}{3}+\frac{t^2}{2}\right) + 6\alpha_5\left(\frac{512t^7}{7}-\frac{1280t^6}{6}+224t^5-100t^4+\frac{46t^3}{3}-\frac{t^2}{2}\right)] + [4t^3\alpha_0 + 8t\alpha_1\left(\frac{2t^3}{3}-\frac{t^2}{2}\right) + \\
& 8t\alpha_2\left(2t^4-\frac{8s^3}{3}+\frac{t^2}{2}\right) + 8t\alpha_3\left(\frac{32t^5}{5}-12t^4+6t^3-\frac{t^2}{2}\right) + 8t\alpha_4\left(\frac{128t^6}{6}-\frac{256t^5}{5}+40t^4-\frac{32t^3}{3}+\frac{t^2}{2}\right) + \\
& 8t\alpha_5\left(\frac{512t^7}{7}-\frac{1280t^6}{6}+224t^5-100t^4+\frac{46t^3}{3}-\frac{t^2}{2}\right)] - [(4t^3\alpha_0 + 4t^2\alpha_1(t^2-s) + 4t^2\alpha_2\left(\frac{8t^3}{3}-4t^2+t\right) \\
& + 4t^2\alpha_3(8t^4-16t^3+9t^2-t)+4t^2\alpha_4\left(\frac{128t^5}{5}-64t^4+\frac{160t^3}{3}-16t^2+s\right)+4t^2\alpha_5\left(\frac{512t^6}{6}+256t^5+ \\
& 280t^4-\frac{400t^3}{3}+23t^2-t\right)] - \left[\frac{4t^3}{3}\alpha_0 + 4\alpha_1\left(\frac{t^4}{2}-\frac{t^3}{3}\right)+4\alpha_2\left(\frac{8t^5}{5}-2t^4+\frac{t^3}{3}\right)+4\alpha_3\left(\frac{32t^6}{6}-\frac{48t^5}{5}+\frac{18t^4}{4}-\right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. \frac{t^3}{3}+4\alpha_4\left(\frac{128t^7}{7}-\frac{256t^6}{6}+32t^5-8t^4-\frac{t^3}{3}\right)+4\alpha_5\left(64t^8-\frac{1280t^7}{7}+\frac{1120t^6}{6}-80t^5+\frac{46t^4}{4}-\frac{t^3}{3}\right)\right] = -2-t-4t^2.
\end{aligned}$$

Collecting like terms,

$$\begin{aligned}
& \alpha_0 - \alpha_1 + \alpha_2 - \alpha_3 + \alpha_4 - \alpha_5 + 2\alpha_1t - 8t\alpha_2 + 18t\alpha_3 - 32t\alpha_4 + 46t\alpha_5 + 8t^2\alpha_2 - \\
& 48t^2\alpha_3 + 160t^2\alpha_4 - 400t^2\alpha_5 - 7t^2\alpha_0 + 7t^2\alpha_1 - 7t^2\alpha_2 + 7t^2\alpha_3 - 7t^2\alpha_4 + 7t^2\alpha_5 - 3t^2\alpha_0 \\
& + 3t^2\alpha_1 - 3t^2\alpha_2 + 3t^2\alpha_3 - 3t^2\alpha_4 + 18t^2\alpha_5 + 32t^3\alpha_3 - 256t^3\alpha_4 + 1120t^3\alpha_5 - 7t^3\alpha_1 + \\
& 28t^3\alpha_2 - 63t^3\alpha_3 + 112t^3\alpha_4 - 161t^3\alpha_5 - 4t^3\alpha_1 + 16t^3\alpha_2 - 36t^3\alpha_3 + 64t^3\alpha_4 - 92t^3\alpha_5 + \\
& 4t^3\alpha_0 - \frac{4t^3}{3}\alpha_0 + \frac{4t^3}{3}\alpha_1 - \frac{4t^3}{3}\alpha_2 + \frac{4t^3}{3}\alpha_3 - \frac{4t^3}{3}\alpha_4 + \frac{4t^3}{3}\alpha_5 + 128t^4\alpha_4 - 1280t^4\alpha_5 - \frac{56t^4}{3}\alpha_2 + \\
& 112t^4\alpha_3 - \frac{1120t^4}{3}\alpha_4 + \frac{2800t^4}{3}\alpha_5 - 12t^4\alpha_2 + 72t^4\alpha_3 - 240t^4\alpha_4 + 600t^4\alpha_5 + \frac{16t^4}{3}\alpha_1 - \frac{64t^4}{3}\alpha_2 \\
& + 48t^4\alpha_3 - \frac{256t^4}{3}\alpha_4 + \frac{368t^4}{3}\alpha_5 - 4t^4\alpha_1 + 16t^4\alpha_2 - 36t^4\alpha_3 + 64t^4\alpha_4 - 92t^4\alpha_5 - 2t^4\alpha_1 + 8t^4\alpha_2 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 18t^4\alpha_3 + 32t^4\alpha_4 - 46t^4\alpha_5 + 512t^5\alpha_5 - 56t^5\alpha_3 + 448t^5\alpha_4 - 1750t^5\alpha_5 - \frac{192t^5}{3}\alpha_3 + \frac{1536t^5}{5}\alpha_4 \\
& - 1344t^5\alpha_5 + 16t^5\alpha_2 - 96t^5\alpha_3 + 320t^5\alpha_4 - 800t^5\alpha_5 - \frac{32t^5}{3}\alpha_2 + 64t^5\alpha_3 - \frac{640t^5}{3}\alpha_4 + \frac{1600t^5}{3}\alpha_5 \\
& - \frac{32t^5}{5}\alpha_2 + \frac{192t^5}{3}\alpha_3 - 128t^5\alpha_4 + 320t^5\alpha_5 - \frac{896t^6}{5}\alpha_4 + 1729t^6\alpha_5 - 128t^6\alpha_4 + 1280t^6\alpha_5 + \\
& \frac{256t^6}{5}\alpha_3 - \frac{2048t^6}{5}\alpha_4 + 1792t^6\alpha_5 - 32t^6\alpha_3 + 256t^6\alpha_4 - 1120t^6\alpha_5 - \frac{64t^6}{3}\alpha_3 + \frac{512t^6}{3}\alpha_4 - \frac{4480t^6}{6}\alpha_5 \\
& - \frac{3584t^7}{7}\alpha_5 - \frac{512t^7}{3}\alpha_4 - \frac{12040t^7}{6}\alpha_5 - \frac{512t^7}{5}\alpha_4 + 1024t^7\alpha_5 - \frac{512t^7}{7}\alpha_4 + \frac{5120t^7}{7}\alpha_5 + \frac{4096t^8}{7}\alpha_5 + \\
& \frac{1024t^8}{3}\alpha_5 - 256t^8\alpha_5 = -2 - t - 4t^2.
\end{aligned}$$

Truncate at t^5 ,

$$\begin{aligned}
& \alpha_0 - \alpha_1 + \alpha_2 - \alpha_3 + \alpha_4 - \alpha_5 + [2\alpha_1 - 8\alpha_2 + 18\alpha_3 - 32\alpha_4 + 46\alpha_5]t + [-10\alpha_0 + 10\alpha_1 - \\
& 2\alpha_2 - 41\alpha_3 + 150\alpha_4 - 375\alpha_5]t^2 + [\frac{8}{3}\alpha_0 + \frac{13}{3}\alpha_1 - \frac{119}{3}\alpha_2 - \frac{197}{3}\alpha_3 - \frac{224}{3}\alpha_4 + \frac{2605}{3}\alpha_5]t^3 + \\
& [-\frac{2}{3}\alpha_1 - 28\alpha_2 + 178\alpha_3 - \frac{776}{3}\alpha_4 + 138\alpha_5]t^4 + [-\frac{16}{15}\alpha_2 - \frac{233}{5}\alpha_3 + \frac{11008}{15}\alpha_4 - \frac{9122}{3}\alpha_5]t^5 + \dots \\
& = -2 - t - 4t^2.
\end{aligned}$$

By comparison;

$$\begin{aligned}
& \alpha_0 - \alpha_1 + \alpha_2 - \alpha_3 + \alpha_4 - \alpha_5 = -2 \\
& 2\alpha_1 - 8\alpha_2 + 18\alpha_3 - 32\alpha_4 + 46\alpha_5 = -1 \\
& -10\alpha_0 + 10\alpha_1 - 2\alpha_2 - 41\alpha_3 + 150\alpha_4 - 375\alpha_5 = -4 \\
& \frac{8}{3}\alpha_0 + \frac{13}{3}\alpha_1 - \frac{119}{3}\alpha_2 - \frac{197}{3}\alpha_3 - \frac{224}{3}\alpha_4 + \frac{2605}{3}\alpha_5 = 0 \\
& -\frac{2}{3}\alpha_1 - 28\alpha_2 + 178\alpha_3 - \frac{776}{3}\alpha_4 + 138\alpha_5 = 0 \\
& -\frac{16}{15}\alpha_2 - \frac{233}{5}\alpha_3 + \frac{11008}{15}\alpha_4 - \frac{9122}{3}\alpha_5 = 0
\end{aligned}$$

Solving for the values of α using Gauss Jordan method(code in appendix),

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & -1 & 1 & -1 & 1 & -1 \\ 0 & 2 & -8 & 18 & -32 & 46 \\ -10 & 10 & -2 & -41 & 150 & -375 \\ \frac{8}{3} & \frac{13}{3} & -\frac{11}{3} & -\frac{197}{3} & -\frac{224}{3} & \frac{2605}{3} \\ 0 & -\frac{2}{3} & -28 & 178 & -\frac{776}{3} & 138 \\ 0 & 0 & -\frac{16}{15} & -\frac{223}{5} & \frac{11008}{15} & -\frac{9122}{3} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \alpha_0 \\ \alpha_1 \\ \alpha_2 \\ \alpha_3 \\ \alpha_4 \\ \alpha_5 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} -2 \\ -1 \\ -4 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

Augmented Matrix:
$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & -1 & 1 & -1 & 1 & -1 & -2 \\ 0 & 2 & -8 & 18 & -32 & 46 & -1 \\ -10 & 10 & -2 & -41 & 150 & -375 & -4 \\ \frac{8}{3} & \frac{13}{3} & -\frac{11}{3} & -\frac{197}{3} & -\frac{224}{3} & \frac{2605}{3} & 0 \\ 0 & -\frac{2}{3} & -28 & 178 & -\frac{776}{3} & 138 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -\frac{16}{15} & -\frac{223}{5} & \frac{11008}{15} & -\frac{9122}{3} & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

Reducing the augmented matrix gives

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 6.035427 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 4.671114 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -2.230903 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & -4.330374 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & -2.441825 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & -0.00599583 \end{pmatrix}$$

Therefore, $\alpha_0 = 6.035427$, $\alpha_1 = -4.671114$, $\alpha_2 = -2.230903$, $\alpha_3 = 3.502160$, $\alpha_4 = -2.441825$, $\alpha_5 = -0.534881$.

$$y(t) = 6.035427 + 4.671114(2t - 1) - 2.230903(8t^2 - 8t + 1) - 4.330374(32t^3 - 48t^2 + 18t - 1) - 2.441825(128t^4 - 256t^3 + 160t^2 - 32t + 1) - 0.00599583(512t^5 - 1280t^4 +$$

$$1120t^3 - 400t^2 + 46t - 1).$$

Simplifying this gives,

$$y(t) = 1.02795483 + 3.66129760t - 12.96208962t^2 + 22.91590624t^3 - 14.35061922t^4 + 3.06986667t^5.$$

Figure 3: Graph of approximate solution $y(t)$

4.4 Graphs and Errors

The exact solution of the Volterra Integral Equation arising from the model of a viscoelastic rod bending quasi statically is $y(t) = e^t$ according to (Reynolds, Appleby & Gyori, 2007).

Figure 4: Graph of exact solution

t	Exact Solution	Approximate Solution	Error = $\ Exact - Analytic\ $
0	1	1.02795483	0.02795483
0.25	1.28402542	1.29649672	0.0124713
0.5	1.64872127	1.67513437	0.0264131
0.75	2.11700002	2.33100752	0.2140075
1.0	2.71828183	3.35332094	0.63503911
1.25	3.49034296	3.72988438	0.23953542
1.5	4.48168907	5.34910741	0.56441834
1.75	5.75460268	6.27453918	0.5199365
2	7.38905610	7.61527183	0.23621573

Table 4.3: Comparison of the exact and approximate solutions

Table 4.1 shows that this method performed well because the errors found is small, the approximate solution is in agreement with the exact solution..

Figure 5: Graph of exact and approximate solution

5 CONCLUSION

In this paper, a numerical method of solving Volterra integral equations was studied. The technique converts the Volterra or Volterra-Hammerstein integral equations into system of algebraic equations using shifted Chebyshev polynomials as basis function. This method is a powerful method for solving linear and nonlinear Volterra equations of all kinds and it is sufficient to give good agreement with the exact solution. The main difference between this and other collocation methods is the replacement of the integral terms by a linear transformation using the Chebyshev differential matrix. The numerical results have been shown and compared with the exact solution in tables and graphs.

What makes this project unique from other researcher's works mentioned in the literature is that unlike the normal Chebyshev collocation methods where Chebyshev polynomial is used as the basis function, this work is a modification and it uses shifted Chebyshev polynomials on $[0, 1]$ as basis.

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APPENDIX

MATLAB code for solving the system of linear equation

%Coefficient matrix

A = [1 -1 1 -1 1 -1 ; 0 2 -8 18 -32 46 ; -10 10 -2 -41 150 -375 ; $\frac{8}{3}$ $\frac{13}{3}$ $-\frac{11}{3}$ $-\frac{197}{3}$ $-\frac{224}{3}$
 $\frac{2605}{3}$; 0 $-\frac{2}{3}$ -28 178 $-\frac{776}{3}$ 138 ; 0 0 $-\frac{16}{15}$ $-\frac{223}{5}$ $\frac{11008}{15}$ $-\frac{9122}{3}$];

% Right-hand side vector

b = [7; 9; 11; 13; 15; 17];

% Augmented matrix

augmentedMatrix = [A b];

% Size of the matrix

[m, n] = size(augmentedMatrix);

% Gauss-Jordan elimination

for i = 1:m

% Pivoting

[i maxRow] = max(abs(augmentedMatrix(i:m, i)));

maxRow = maxRow + i - 1;

augmentedMatrix([i maxRow], :) = augmentedMatrix([maxRow i], :);

% Row operations

pivot = augmentedMatrix(i, i);

augmentedMatrix(i, :) = augmentedMatrix(i, :) / pivot;

for j = 1:m

if j \neq i

```
factor = augmentedMatrix(j, i);
augmentedMatrix(j, :) = augmentedMatrix(j, :) - factor * augmentedMatrix(i, :);
    end
end
end
    % Extracting solution
solution = augmentedMatrix(:, end);

    disp('Solution:');
disp(solution);
```